

Lexico-discursive analysis of emotions adapted to the context of decision-making in trading based on the article by Harmon-Jones et al. (2016)¹.

Emotion analyzed	Encouragement to write a story	A word that best describes the emotion felt	Four more words to describe emotion
Anger	Develop a specific memory during the experiment in which the general market configuration did not correspond to your expectations and had a negative effect on the financial value of your portfolio. Specify your emotional response to this situation.		
Disgust	Develop a specific memory of a moment during the experiment when you felt something very unpleasant. Specify your emotional feelings about the situation.		
Fear	Recall a specific moment when you felt you were in danger with regard to the financial value of your portfolio (i.e. a situation for which you didn't know how to react and cope). Specify your emotional feelings in relation to this situation.		
Anxiety	Think back to a specific moment when you anticipated a negative development in the financial value of your portfolio. You really wanted something not to happen, but you thought		

¹ Harmon-Jones C, Bastian B, Harmon-Jones E (2016). The Discrete Emotions Questionnaire: A New Tool for Measuring State Self-Reported Emotions. PLoS ONE 11(8), 25 pages)

	that this unpleasant outcome would happen soon. Specify your emotional feelings in relation to this scenario.		
Sadness	Recall a particular moment during the experiment when you experienced a significant financial loss that would be difficult or impossible to overcome. Describe your emotional feelings in this case.		
Desire	Remember a specific moment when you anticipated a positive change in the value of your positive portfolio in the future. You really wanted something, and you thought the result you hoped for would happen soon. Describe your emotional feelings in this case.		
Joy	Remember a particular moment when something very positive had just happened. This moment corresponds to the achievement of an important goal. Describe how you felt emotionally.		